

CREATING AN $n = 4$ PANCAKE GRAPH IN 3D

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ABSTRACT. Graph theory has a problem called the “Pancake Problem”, which asks how many flip operations are required to sort pancakes of different sizes in order from the smallest to the largest by using only a spatula. It is concerned with sorting a permutation (a stack of pancakes of different sizes) using only prefix reversals (operations of pancake flipping). In this research, to study the relationships between permutations that result from flip operations, a pancake graph is constructed for $n = 4$. When the graph is created in 3D, a highly symmetric three-layer structure is obtained. In addition, we succeed in applying the structure to a new form by putting four hexagons in the positions of each face of a regular tetrahedron.

1. INTRODUCTION

In 1975, Jacob E. Goodman (under the pseudonym Harry Dweighter [1]) first posed the following problem:

The chef in our place is sloppy, and when he prepares a stack of pancakes, they come out all different sizes. Therefore, when I deliver them to a customer, on the way to the table I rearrange them (so that the smallest winds up on top, and so on, down to the largest at the bottom) by grabbing several from the top and flipping them over, repeating this (varying the number I flip) as many times as necessary. If there are n pancakes, what is the maximum number of flips (in terms of n) that I will ever have to use to rearrange them?

The “Pancake Problem” asks how many prefix reversals are sufficient to sort any permutation to the identity [3].

A pancake flipping refers to the operation where, in a stack of n (the number of pancakes) pancakes of different sizes, a number of pancakes from the top are flipped simultaneously. In pancake flipping, when “**flip** $_j$ ” indicates the operation of flipping j pancakes from the top, **flip** $_2$, **flip** $_3$, and **flip** $_4$ correspond to the transpositions $(1\ 2)$, $(1\ 3)$, and $(1\ 4)(2\ 3)$, respectively.

The flip operation to arrange pancakes (which can be represented by a permutation rearrangement by flipping) can be illustrated in the pancake graph, which is a Cayley graph of the symmetric group \mathfrak{S}_n . The value of the maximum distance between two vertices, which is called the diameter of the pancake graph, is evaluated by inequality (e.g. [2]). But the exact value for an arbitrary large n is unknown (see [4]).

On the other hand, in the case where $n = 4$, we are able to examine the relationship of permutations by using the Hasse diagram of \mathfrak{S}_4 based on the Bruhat order and the bubble-sort graph, which is the Cayley graph of \mathfrak{S}_4 with respect to the generating set $\{(1\ 2), (2\ 3), (3\ 4)\}$. When the Hasse diagram is grasped in 3D, the form is called a truncated octahedron, which covers the lack of symmetry of the

Hasse diagram. Following the structures of the Hasse diagram and the truncated octahedron, in this research, we consider whether it is possible to represent the performance of flipping on permutations in a 3D graphic form so that it becomes easy to grasp visually.

FIGURE 1. **The Hasse diagram and the truncated octahedron.** A comparison between the Hasse diagram of the symmetric group \mathfrak{S}_4 based on the Bruhat order (left) and its realization as a truncated octahedron in 3D space (right).

2. MAIN RESULT

It is known that the pancake graph of degree n consists of n sets of the pancake graph of degree $n - 1$. In this research, we grasp an $n = 4$ pancake graph in 3D in order to contribute to better understanding of the performance of flipping in permutations.

The following theorem is our main result (see Figure 9):

Theorem 1. *There exists a continuous map $f : P_4 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$ such that its restriction $f|_{V_4}$ to V_4 is injective, and for any $\sigma \in \mathfrak{S}_4$, the sets $f(V_4)$, $f(E_{4,2})$, $f(E_{4,3})$, and $f(E_{4,4})$ are invariant under $\rho(\sigma)$.*

In the theorem above, P_4 is the pancake graph for $n = 4$, and V_4 is its vertex set. $E_{4,2}$, $E_{4,3}$, and $E_{4,4}$ are the edge set of P_4 corresponding to the flip operations \mathbf{flip}_2 , \mathbf{flip}_3 and \mathbf{flip}_4 , respectively. $\rho : \mathfrak{S}_4 \rightarrow \text{GL}_3(\mathbb{R})$ is a well-known representation of \mathfrak{S}_4 .

3. PRELIMINARIES

3.1. Permutations. A *permutation* is a rearrangement of the numbers $1, 2, \dots$, and n . We denote a permutation π rearranging $1, 2, \dots$, and n into $\pi(1), \pi(2), \dots$, and $\pi(n)$ as $\pi = [\pi(1) \pi(2) \cdots \pi(n)] \in \mathfrak{S}_n$.

A *transposition* is an exchange of two numbers in a permutation. Notice that performing a transposition on a permutation from right makes the two numbers exchange their positions as the transposition indicates.

For instance, transposition $(1\ 2)$ performed on the permutation $[3\ 4\ 1\ 2]$ is written as

$$[3\ 4\ 1\ 2] \circ (1\ 2) = [4\ 3\ 1\ 2]$$

(In this operation, the permutation $[3\ 4\ 1\ 2]$ becomes the permutation $[4\ 3\ 1\ 2]$.)

An *adjacent transposition* is a transposition that exchanges natural numbers whose difference is one.

3.2. Pancake Graph. Let $flip_j \in \mathfrak{S}_n$ ($j \in \{2, 3, \dots, n\}$) be the permutation

$$flip_j(i) = \begin{cases} j - i + 1 & (\text{if } i \leq j), \\ i & (\text{if } i > j). \end{cases}$$

Then the set $\{flip_j | j \in \{2, 3, \dots, n\}\}$ is a generating set of \mathfrak{S}_n . The Cayley graph of \mathfrak{S}_n with respect to the generating set $\{flip_j | j \in \{2, 3, \dots, n\}\}$ is called the *pancake graph* P_n of degree n . Specifically, the vertex set V_n of $P_n = (V_n, E_n)$ is $V_n = \mathfrak{S}_n$, and the edge set E_n is given by

$$E_n = \{\{\pi, \pi \circ flip_j\} | \pi \in \mathfrak{S}_n, j \in \{2, 3, \dots, n\}\}.$$

Remark 1. (1) For each $j \in \{2, 3, \dots, n\}$, define $E_{n,j} := \{\{\pi, \pi \circ flip_j\} | \pi \in \mathfrak{S}_n\}$.

If $\pi' = \pi \circ flip_j$, then $\pi = \pi' \circ flip_j$ also holds. Thus we have $|E_{n,j}| = \frac{n!}{2}$. Each edge in $E_{n,j}$ corresponds to the operation \mathbf{flip}_j defined in the next section.

(2) Hereafter, we identify the vertex set V_n with \mathfrak{S}_n . By regarding each edge $\{\pi, \pi'\}$ as a path of length 1 connecting the two points π and π' , the pancake graph P_n can be viewed as a metric space.

Example 1. The $n = 2$ pancake graph. (If $n = 2$, the flip operation performed is only \mathbf{flip}_2 .)

FIGURE 2. **The pancake graph P_2 .** Geometric representation of the graph for degree $n = 2$, where the only valid prefix reversal is the \mathbf{flip}_2 operation.

Example 2. The $n = 3$ pancake graph. (If $n = 3$, the flip operation performed is \mathbf{flip}_2 and \mathbf{flip}_3 .)

In Figure 3, the edges in $E_{3,2}$ (*i.e.* the edges corresponding to \mathbf{flip}_2) are represented by blue lines, and the edges (*i.e.* the edges corresponding to \mathbf{flip}_2) in $E_{3,3}$ by green lines.

4. $n = 4$ PANCAKE FLIPPING

Consider an arrangement of n pancakes of different sizes, and flip the pancakes from the top.

FIGURE 3. **The pancake graph P_3 .** Visualization of the $n = 3$ graph where blue edges denote \mathbf{flip}_2 transpositions and green edges denote \mathbf{flip}_3 prefix reversals.

4.1. **$n = 4$ Case.** Consider the flipping in the situation of $n = 4$. We number the pancakes 1, 2, 3, and 4 from the smallest to the largest to represent the arrangement of the pancakes. For instance, the arrangement of pancakes in Figure 4a is represented as the permutation $[1\ 2\ 3\ 4]$. We define the operation of flipping j pancakes from the top as \mathbf{flip}_j .

4.2. **\mathbf{flip}_2 .** The definition of \mathbf{flip}_2 is “the operation of flipping 2 pancakes from the top”, which means the first and second pancakes exchange their positions. This corresponds to the transposition $(1\ 2)$, and the stack of pancakes in Figure 4b shows the result of performing \mathbf{flip}_2 on the stack of pancakes in Figure 4a.
 $\mathbf{flip}_2 := (1\ 2)$

4.3. **\mathbf{flip}_3 .** The definition of \mathbf{flip}_3 is “the operation of flipping 3 pancakes from the top”, which means the first and third pancakes are exchanged, leaving the second pancake to stay. This corresponds to the transposition $(1\ 3)$, and the stack of pancakes in Figure 4c shows the result of performing \mathbf{flip}_3 on the stack of pancakes in Figure 4a.
 $\mathbf{flip}_3 := (1\ 3)$

4.4. **\mathbf{flip}_4 .** The definition of \mathbf{flip}_4 is “the operation of flipping 4 pancakes from the top”, which means all 4 pancakes are turned upside down so that the first and fourth pancakes exchange and the second and third pancakes exchange their positions. This corresponds to the permutation, and the stack of pancakes in Figure 4d shows the result of performing \mathbf{flip}_4 on the stack of pancakes in Figure 4a.
 $\mathbf{flip}_4 := (1\ 4)(2\ 3)$

FIGURE 4. **Standard prefix reversal operations on $n = 4$ pancakes.** Figures (a) through (d) illustrate the identity configuration and the results of the three generating flips.

Upon the set of the permutation of degree n , the graph that is made by connecting permutations that transition into each other through pancake flipping is called a pancake graph. This graph connects permutations, indicating permutations as vertices and flippings as edges.

5. AN $n = 4$ PANCAKE GRAPH

5.1. Our first attempt: Since there are $4! = 24$ permutations of degree four, the pancake graph for $n = 4$ has 24 vertices. We attempt to create a symmetric 2D pancake graph for $n = 4$ by connecting permutations starting from the permutation $[1\ 2\ 3\ 4]$, the base. However, when drawing the graph with the rule in which permutations connected by the same number of edges from the permutation $[1\ 2\ 3\ 4]$, the base, are placed in the same layer, we find that some permutations in the same layer are adjacent to each other, resulting in a complicated diagram. Therefore, in this study, we shall consider the pancake graph in 3D.

5.2. The use of Euler's polyhedron formula: In the process of creating a three-dimensional pancake graph, we use Euler's polyhedron formula to predict the shape of the pancake graph.

Euler's polyhedron formula: If the polyhedron has v vertices, e edges, and f faces, then $v - e + f = 2$

In a pancake graph, permutations correspond to vertices, so for the permutations of degree four, there are 24 permutations, so $v = 24$. Three types of flip, there are 36 of them in total, so $e = 36$. Therefore, we get 14 for f and predict that the shape is a tetradecahedron.

In the figures below, the edges for $\mathbf{flip}_2 = (1\ 2)$ are represented by blue lines, the edges for $\mathbf{flip}_3 = (1\ 3)$ by green lines, and the edges for $\mathbf{flip}_4 = (1\ 4)(2\ 3)$ by red lines.

We first consider the faces formed by each pair of flips (edges).

Case 1. For the face formed by $\mathbf{flip}_2 = (1\ 2)$, and $\mathbf{flip}_3 = (1\ 3)$, starting from the base permutation $[1\ 2\ 3\ 4]$, we obtain $[1\ 2\ 3\ 4] \circ (1\ 2) \circ (1\ 3) = [3\ 1\ 2\ 4]$, which gives the mapping $1 \mapsto 3$, $2 \mapsto 1$, $3 \mapsto 2$, and $4 \mapsto 4$. To return to the original permutation $[1\ 2\ 3\ 4]$, The numbers return to their initial position by three steps ($1 \mapsto 3 \mapsto 2 \mapsto 1$), so three sets of green and blue edges are needed. Forming a hexagon as shown in Figure 5a, four such hexagons are created in total.

Case 2. For the face formed by $\mathbf{flip}_2 = (1\ 2)$, and $\mathbf{flip}_4 = (1\ 4)(2\ 3)$, starting from $[1\ 2\ 3\ 4]$, we obtain $[1\ 2\ 3\ 4] \circ (1\ 2) \circ (1\ 4)(2\ 3) = [4\ 3\ 1\ 2]$, which gives the mapping $1 \mapsto 4$, $2 \mapsto 3$, $3 \mapsto 1$, and $4 \mapsto 2$. The numbers return to their initial positions by four steps ($1 \mapsto 4 \mapsto 2 \mapsto 3 \mapsto 1$), so four sets of green and red edges are needed. Forming an octagon as shown in Figure 5b, three such octagons are created in total.

Case 3. For the face formed by $\mathbf{flip}_3 = (1\ 3)$, and $\mathbf{flip}_4 = (1\ 4)(2\ 3)$, starting from $[1\ 2\ 3\ 4]$, we obtain $[1\ 2\ 3\ 4] \circ (1\ 3) \circ (1\ 4)(2\ 3) = [4\ 1\ 2\ 3]$, which gives the mapping $1 \mapsto 4$, $2 \mapsto 1$, $3 \mapsto 2$, and $4 \mapsto 3$. The numbers return to their initial positions by four steps ($1 \mapsto 4 \mapsto 3 \mapsto 2 \mapsto 1$), so four sets of green and red edges are needed. Forming an octagon as shown in Figure 5c, three such octagons are created in total.

(Results)

Since there are 24 permutations of degree four in total, and three edges can be drawn

FIGURE 5. **Canonical cycles in the P_4 pancake graph.** (a) The hexagonal cycle formed by alternating flip_2 and flip_3 . (b, c) The two distinct types of octagonal cycles formed by alternating $\text{flip}_2/\text{flip}_4$ and $\text{flip}_3/\text{flip}_4$ operations, respectively.

from a permutation, we need four hexagons with blue edges and green edges, three octagons with green edges and red edges, and three octagons with blue and red edges. In other words, an $n = 4$ pancake graph consists of ten polygons, which contradicts our prediction based on Euler's polyhedron formula that an $n = 4$ pancake graph is a tetradecahedron in 3D. Therefore, it is impossible to form a polyhedron by combining these polygons.

FIGURE 6. **Assembled wireframe model of the $n = 4$ pancake graph.** This physical realization demonstrates the three-layer structure and the highly symmetric connectivity resulting from the three types of flip operations.

By using wire for the edges, we are able to create a three-layer structure as shown in Figure 6. Regarding the structure of Figure 6, each layer is depicted in Figure 7. This structure has four hexagons, formed by flip_2 and flip_3 (from Figure 5a), arranged on the sides, connected to an octagon on the top layer (formed by flip_3

and \mathbf{flip}_4 , from Figure 5c) and an octagon on the bottom layer (formed by \mathbf{flip}_2 and \mathbf{flip}_4 , from Figure 5b).

FIGURE 7. **Layer-wise decomposition of the P_4 3D structure.** The model is partitioned into three distinct layers to illustrate the rotational symmetry of the hexagonal and octagonal faces.

Focusing on the fact that our structure contains four hexagons, we consider whether it is possible to place those hexagons on the positions of each face of a regular tetrahedron. The hexagons, which we place as the bases, consist of \mathbf{flip}_2 and \mathbf{flip}_3 . This means that transpositions are performed on numbers except the fourth one, and the fourth number of all six permutations in the same hexagon is consistent. Also, we can find that for the red edges, which represent \mathbf{flip}_4 , two pieces are drawn from each hexagon. So, in applying the structure to a new form, we need to focus on these and connect the edges. We attempt to create a highly symmetrical structure by positioning the four hexagons from Figure 5a on the faces of a regular tetrahedron. By connecting the edges based on the rule that the shape does not change its shape, no matter how it is rotated (shown in Figure 7), the new form is obtained (Figure 9).

5.3. Highly Symmetrical Form. Let $\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3 \in \mathfrak{S}_4$ be defined as $\sigma_1 := (1\ 2)$, $\sigma_2 := (3\ 4)$, and $\sigma_3 := (2\ 3\ 4)$. These form a generating set of \mathfrak{S}_4 . The symmetric group \mathfrak{S}_4 acts isometrically on \mathbb{R}^3 from the left via the representation $\rho : \mathfrak{S}_4 \rightarrow \text{GL}_3(\mathbb{R})$ defined by

$$\rho(\sigma_1) = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{3} & 0 & -\frac{2\sqrt{2}}{3} \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\frac{2\sqrt{2}}{3} & 0 & -\frac{1}{3} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \rho(\sigma_2) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \rho(\sigma_3) = \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & 0 \\ -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Remark 2. Let $v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4 \in \mathbb{R}^3$ be

$$v_1 := \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad v_2 := \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{2\sqrt{2}}{3} \\ 0 \\ -\frac{1}{3} \end{pmatrix}, \quad v_3 := \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\sqrt{2}}{3} \\ \frac{\sqrt{6}}{3} \\ -\frac{1}{3} \end{pmatrix}, \quad v_4 := \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\sqrt{2}}{3} \\ -\frac{\sqrt{6}}{3} \\ -\frac{1}{3} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then, these are the vertices of a regular tetrahedron centered at the origin, and for any $\sigma \in \mathfrak{S}_4$, $\rho(\sigma)(v_i) = v_{\sigma(i)}$ holds for $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$.

Theorem 1. *There exists a continuous map $f : P_4 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$ such that its restriction $f|_{V_4}$ to V_4 is injective, and for any $\sigma \in \mathfrak{S}_4$, the sets $f(V_4)$, $f(E_{4,2})$, $f(E_{4,3})$, and $f(E_{4,4})$ are invariant under $\rho(\sigma)$.*

Proof. For $\pi = [\pi(1) \ \pi(2) \ \pi(3) \ \pi(4)] \in V_4$, define $f(\pi) = \frac{1}{3}v_{\pi(1)} + \frac{1}{6}v_{\pi(2)} + \frac{1}{2}v_{\pi(3)}$. Then, for any π such that $\pi(4) = d$, the point $f(\pi)$ lies on the triangle formed by the vertices v_a, v_b, v_c , and such 6 points form a hexagon, where $\{a, b, c, d\} = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$ (Figure 8). Consequently, the restriction $f|_{V_4}$ is injective.

FIGURE 8. $f(P_4)$ in the triangle formed by the vertices v_a, v_b, v_c

Furthermore, by Remark 2, for any $\sigma \in \mathfrak{S}_4$, we have:

$$\rho(\sigma)f(\pi) = \rho(\sigma)(f([\pi(1) \ \pi(2) \ \pi(3) \ \pi(4)])) = f([\sigma(\pi(1)) \ \sigma(\pi(2)) \ \sigma(\pi(3)) \ \sigma(\pi(4))]) = f(\sigma \circ \pi),$$

which implies that $f(V_4)$ is invariant under $\rho(\sigma)$. Regarding the edges, each $\{\pi, \pi \circ \text{flip}_j\} \in E_{4,j}$ can be mapped continuously to the line segment connecting $f(\pi)$ and $f(\pi \circ \text{flip}_j)$. Then, similarly, since $\rho(\sigma)f(\pi) = f(\sigma \circ \pi)$ and

$$\rho(\sigma)f(\pi \circ \text{flip}_j) = f(\sigma \circ (\pi \circ \text{flip}_j)) = f((\sigma \circ \pi) \circ \text{flip}_j),$$

it follows that $f(E_{4,j})$ is also invariant under $\rho(\sigma)$. \square

FIGURE 9. $f(P_4)$

Figure 9 demonstrates how $f(P_4)$ lies in \mathbb{R}^3 . This figure is available on <https://www.geogebra.org/calculator/sjfnx9n6>, where the figure can be rotated and viewed from any angle. A movie in which the figure rotates around an axis is also available on <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1PuAIyi7m9yiGT8TxJIZKfdPdyuVTDZtY/view>.

6. PROSPECTS

In this research, we obtain a three-layer structure with high symmetry when the graph is created in three dimensions. In addition to the fact that the performances of adjacent transpositions can be grasped using a truncated octahedron, we succeed in showing the performance of flipping in a simple 3D graphic form. However, we cannot grasp the relationship of permutations by the performance of flipping at a glance with this structure. As our prospect, we will analyze the new form of the structure that we have introduced, and will approach the examination of the diameter of the pancake graph.

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